

In [51]:

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn import datasets
from sklearn import svm
import nltk
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfTransformer
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import CountVectorizer
from sklearn.naive_bayes import MultinomialNB
from sklearn.pipeline import Pipeline
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, f1_score, precision_score, recall_score, classification_report, confusion_matrix
```

In [39]:

```
df = pd.read_csv('training.txt', header=None, sep='\t', names=['Text', 'Label'])
df2 = df[df.Label.notnull()]
```

In [41]:

```
data = df2['Text'].tolist()
labels = df2['Label'].tolist()
```

In [42]:

```
labels = [int(i) for i in labels]
```

In [44]:

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(data, labels, test_size=0.3,
random_state=0)
```

In [47]:

```
text_clf = Pipeline([('vect', CountVectorizer()),
                    ('tfidf', TfidfTransformer()),
                    ('clf', MultinomialNB()),
                    ])
text_clf = text_clf.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

In [48]:

```
predicted = text_clf.predict(X_test)
np.mean(predicted == y_test)
```

Out[48]:

```
0.9079365079365079
```

In [50]:

```
confusion_matrix(y_test, predicted)
```

Out[50]:

```
array([[247,  1],  
       [ 28, 39]])
```

In [52]:

```
print(f1_score(y_test, predicted, average="macro"))  
print(precision_score(y_test, predicted, average="macro"))  
print(recall_score(y_test, predicted, average="macro"))
```

```
0.8367613159164419  
0.936590909090909  
0.7890286470871449
```

In []:

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